

Supplemental Materials

Computational design of α -AsP/ γ -AsP vertical two-dimensional homojunction for photovoltaic applications

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1. Thermal stability of α -AsP/ γ -AsP homojunction with AA stacking

Fig. S1 The molecular dynamics simulation of AA-stacking. We used 10,000 steps of molecular dynamics simulation to verify its dynamic stability.

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Fig. S2 Comparison diagram of α -AsP/ γ -AsP homojunction simulated by molecular dynamics. (a) Top view and (b) side view, respectively.

It can be found from Figure S1 that the free energy fluctuates in a narrow range (-655 eV~-653 eV). In Figure S2, by comparing the initial structure with the structure after molecular dynamics simulation, we can find that the structure is very stable.

2. Phonon dispersion of monolayer α -AsP, monolayer γ -AsP and α -AsP/ γ -AsP homojunction

Fig. S3 Phonon dispersion of (a) monolayer α -AsP, (b) monolayer γ -AsP and (c) α -AsP/ γ -AsP homojunction

To verify the dynamic stability of the material, we calculated the phonon spectra of monolayer α -AsP, monolayer γ -AsP and α -AsP/ γ -AsP homojunction, respectively. The calculated results show that above three structures are stable due to no imaginary frequency is existed, which indicates that their dynamic characteristics are very stable.